

Analysis of Nonlinear Vibration of Hybrid Composite Plates

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Using the Lagrangian equation, the nonlinear vibration analysis of laminated hybrid composite plates is carried out. The effects of stacking sequences, aspect ratios, number of modes, number of layers and elastic properties on the nonlinear vibration are investigated. The presence of bending-extension coupling in antisymmetric plates yields a second power term in addition to a cubic nonlinear term in the governing differential equation of motion. But for symmetric plate case, this second term vanishes. The fundamental frequency of analytic results are compared with that of ABAQUS FEM analysis. For the nonlinear vibration of antisymmetric unimaterial plate, the result of reference is presented for comparison with this result.

Keywords : Lagrangian equation, nonlinear vibration, hybrid composite plates, stacking sequences

1. Introduction

Laminated composite materials are becoming of great importance in many advanced technology areas. This is due to the excellent mechanical properties of these materials, such as the high stiffness-to-weight ratio and high strength-to-weight ratio. Using the properties of materials, we can make thin-walled structures in engineering fields. But because the system of thin-walled structure can be vibrated with large amplitude in dynamic behavior, it is not sufficient to employ the classical linear theory to analyze their large amplitude vibration behavior. Then, Chia[1] presented much information on the nonlinear response of plate in his book. And Bennet[2], Chandra and Raju[3] reported the nonlinear vibration of the anti-symmetric laminated angle-ply plates. Chandra and Raju[4] studied the nonlinear vibration of simply-supported cross-ply rectangular plates, wherein the two term perturbation method is employed to solve the nonlinear governing equation. Reddy and Chao[5] employed the FEM to study the nonlinear response of anisotropic plates. And Whitney and Leissa[6], Bert[7] analyzed the nonlinear vibration of anti-symmetric cross-ply plate considering the extension-bending coupling effect. Recently, Singh and Rao[8] investigated the nonlinear vibration behavior of antisymmetric cross-ply plates considering the effect of extension-bending coupling using the direct numerical integration method.

But above mentioned reseachers analyzed the plates laminated with only one material, there is no information on hybrid plates which are laminated with various materials in each layer. Therefore in this study, the nonlinear vibration of hybrid plate laminated with aluminium, GFRP, CFRP and BFRP is carried out considering extension-bending coupling effect in laminated plates using the Lagrangian equation. And the effect of various stacking sequences in plates is examined for nonlinear vibration. The effect of aspect ratios, vibration modes and elastic coefficient ratios is investigated also. The nonlinear frequencies for a plate laminated with one material-CFRP are compared with the available solutions in Ref.[8]. Also, fundamental linear frequencies of present method are presented for comparison with those of FEM program, ABAQUS[9].

2. Formulation

Consider the thin rectangular hybrid plates of total thickness h composed of many cross-ply orthotropic, isotropic layers. The origin of the Cartesian coordinate system is located in one coner of the mid-plane(x - y plane) with the z -axis is perpendicular to this plane as shown in Figure 1(a),

and its section shown in Figure 1(b).

For these plates von Karman type nonlinear strain-displacement relations are used to analyze the large amplitude nonlinear vibration.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= u_{,x} + \frac{w_{,x}^2}{2} & \varepsilon_2 &= v_{,y} + \frac{w_{,y}^2}{2} & \varepsilon_6 &= u_{,y} + v_{,x} + w_{,x}w_{,y} \\ \kappa_1 &= -w_{,xx} & \kappa_2 &= -w_{,yy} & \kappa_6 &= -w_{,xy} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where, u, v, w are mid-plane displacements of x, y, z directions respectively.

The constitutive equations of laminated composite plate are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_i \\ M_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{ij} & B_{ij} \\ B_{ij} & D_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_j \\ \kappa_j \end{Bmatrix}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 6 \quad (2)$$

where N, M are stresses and moment resultants per unit length respectively. And A, B, D are the respective extension, extension-bending coupling, bending stiffness coefficients, defined as follows:

$$A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} C_{ij}^{(k)}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (3)$$

where z_{k-1} is the distance from the mid-plane to the lower surface of the $(k-1)$ th layer. The potential energy(P) of an antisymmetric cross-ply laminates can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} P = \frac{1}{2} \int \int [& A_{11}\varepsilon_1^2 + 2A_{12}\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2 + A_{22}\varepsilon_2^2 + A_{66}\varepsilon_6^2 + 2B_{11}\varepsilon_1\kappa_1 + 2B_{22}\varepsilon_2\kappa_2 \\ & + D_{11}\kappa_1^2 + 2D_{12}\kappa_1\kappa_2 + D_{22}\kappa_2^2 + D_{66}\kappa_6^2] dx dy \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Neglecting the in-plane inertia, the kinetic energy is expressed as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int \int [\sum \rho_k h_k] \dot{w}^2 dx dy \quad (5)$$

where ρ_k and h_k are density and thickness of k -th layer. And $(\dot{})$ is the derivative to time.

Considered boundary conditions are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u(0,y) &= u(a,y) = u(x,0) = u(x,b) = 0 \\ v(0,y) &= v(a,y) = v(x,0) = v(x,b) = 0 \\ w(0,y) &= w(a,y) = w(x,0) = w(x,b) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The followings are admissible displacement functions satisfying above immovable edge condition.

$$\begin{aligned} u(x,y,t) &= U(t) \sin \frac{2m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \\ v(x,y,t) &= V(t) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{2n\pi y}{b} \\ w(x,y,t) &= W(t) \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Applying Equation 6 to Equation 1 and substituting this results into energy Equations(4,5) gives as

$$\begin{aligned} P = \frac{ab}{8} [& F_8 W^2 + F_6 U^2 + F_3 V^2 + 2F_5 UW + 2F_1 VW \\ & + 2F_7 UW^2 + 2F_2 UV + 2F_4 VW^2 + \frac{2}{3} F_9 W^3 + \frac{1}{2} F_{10} W^4] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$T = \frac{ab}{8} [\sum_{k=1}^N \rho_k h_k] \dot{W}^2 \quad (9)$$

where each coefficients are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= -\frac{4C_n}{3n\pi} X^3 B_{22} \\ F_2 &= \frac{16C_m}{9mn\pi^2} XY(A_{12} + A_{66}) \\ F_3 &= X^2 A_{66} + 4Y^2 A_{22} \\ F_4 &= \frac{C_m}{3m\pi} \{ 2Y^3 A_{22} - X^2 Y(A_{12} - A_{66}) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_6 &= 4X^2A_{11} + Y^2A_{66} \\
F_7 &= \frac{C_n}{3n\pi} \{2X^3A_{11} - XY^2(A_{12} - A_{66})\} \\
F_8 &= X^4D_{11} + 2X^2Y^2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) + Y^4D_{22} \\
F_9 &= \frac{4C_{mn}}{3mn\pi^2} (X^4B_{11} + Y^4B_{22}) \\
F_{10} &= \frac{9}{32} (X^4A_{11} + A_{22}) + \frac{1}{16} X^2Y^2(A_{12} + 2A_{66})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{where, } X &= m\pi/a \\
Y &= n\pi/b \\
C_m &= 1 + (-1)^m \\
C_n &= 1 + (-1)^n \\
C_{mn} &= C_m C_n
\end{aligned}$$

Using the Lagrangian equation to solve the vibration problem, we can derive the equation of motion.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial L}{\partial U} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{U}} &= 0 \\
\frac{\partial L}{\partial V} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{V}} &= 0 \\
\frac{\partial L}{\partial W} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{W}} &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where Lagrangian $L = P - T$

The relation of U and W is derived from the first equation of Equation 9 and the relation of V and W from the second of Equation 9. Next, substituting those results into the third of Equation 9, the equation of motion can be derived as follows:

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^{k=N} \rho_k h_k \right) \dot{W} + \alpha W + \beta W^2 + \gamma W^3 = 0 \tag{11}$$

Here, dot is derivative to time and α is linear stiffness coefficient and β, γ are nonlinear stiffness coefficients.

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha &= F_8 + \frac{2F_1F_2F_5 - F_3F_5^2 - F_1^2F_6}{F_3F_6 - F_2^2} \\
\beta &= F_9 + \frac{3(F_2F_4F_5 + F_1F_2F_7 - F_3F_5F_7 - F_1F_4F_6)}{F_3F_6 - F_2^2} \\
\gamma &= F_{10} + \frac{2(2F_2F_4F_7 - F_3F_7^2 - F_4F_6^2)}{F_3F_6 - F_2^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

3. Numerical Results and Discussion

The plates considered in this study are hybrid laminated with GFRP, CFRP, BFRP and Aluminium, and Table 1 shows the used material properties.

Based on Equation 11, the numerical results are solved using RUNGE-KUTTA Method. Figure 2 shows variation of non-dimensional amplitude to time of hybrid anti-symmetric laminated plate with CFRP and BFRP, [0°/90°], having aspect ratio 1 and 2 ($a=0.25m$), ratio of width to thickness, $a/h=80$. For a aspect ratio=1 plate (i.e. square plate), positive and negative amplitude are same, whereas for a aspect ratio=2 plate (rectangular plate), these are not same that positive amplitude is larger than negative amplitude. For rectangular antisymmetric two-layered hybrid plates, this trend means that the initial excitation direction is very important. This reason is that power nonlinear term β , which is constituted with bending-extension coupling term B_{ψ} , governs the equation of

term β , which is constituted with bending-extension coupling term B_{ij} , governs the equation of motion mainly in the case of rectangular plates. In Table 2, the nonlinear frequency ratios are compared with results of Ref.[8] using direct integral method for square and rectangular antisymmetric two layers cross-ply plates laminated with CFRP $E_1/E_2=40$, $E_2/G_{12}=0.5$, $\nu_{12}=0.25$. The results obtained from both method agrees well with each other. Generally, the square plate has larger nonlinearity than the rectangular plate.

The effects of stacking sequences for antisymmetric hybrid rectangular plate is shown in Figure 3, where 0° , 90° are laminated with BFRP and CFRP respectively. For 2 layers plate it shows softening type in small amplitude which decreases frequency ratios with the increase of amplitude. And antisymmetric lay-up has different amplitude to the 0 axis of frequency ratio and nonlinearity in negative region is larger than positive one. In this figure, the nonlinearity decreases with the increase of layer number for negative amplitude, but for positive amplitude it has reverse pattern. When laminate has more 4 layers, nonlinearity is almost uniform.

Figure 4 shows behavior of nonlinearity in effect of various aspect ratios in $[Al/0^\circ_c/90^\circ/Al]$ hybrid plate with laminated Al and CFRP. The larger aspect ratio, the larger nonlinearity. This is because nonlinear term β , γ govern equation of motion, especially, β is more significant.

In Figure 5, the effect of x-direction half wave number m is investigated for symmetrically laminated with Al and CFRP, $[Al/0^\circ_c]_s$ hybrid plate. The increase of half wave number indicates increase of mode. The higher mode, the higher nonlinearity.

The effects of Young's modulus and layer angle of $[\theta^\circ/Al]_s$ and $[Al/\theta^\circ]_s$ symmetric layer-up plate are presented in Figure 6 and 7. In case of $[\theta^\circ/Al]_s$, decrease of Young's modulus E_1 increases of nonlinearity, which is reason that increase of Young's modulus E_1 reduces nonlinear term γ . That is, GFRP hybrid plate has the largest nonlinearity, BFRP has the smallest. And 0° layer-up is more nonlinear than 90° layer-up. $[Al/\theta^\circ]_s$ hybrid plate in Figure 7 has reverse trend.

In Table 3, the linear fundamental frequencies present for $a=b=0.25$, $a/h=80$ hybrid symmetric laminated plates with various stacking sequences and material properties. This analytic results agree well with ABAQUS results well. For $[0^\circ/Al]_s$, the frequencies increase as Young's modulus E_1 increases. And the frequencies for $[Al/0^\circ]_s$ case increase with increase of E_1/E_2 ratio, this means the E_2 is very important factor in this laminate plate. Meanwhile, as bending stiffness of $[0^\circ/Al]_s$ is larger than that of $[Al/0^\circ]_s$, the $[0^\circ/Al]_s$ hybrid plates have higher frequencies.

4. Conclusions

For the hybrid laminated plates, the nonlinear vibration behavior is investigated. In the case of antisymmetric laminated hybrid plate, it shows softening behavior in initial small amplitude for square plate and then change to hardening behavior. And if it has 2 or more layers, the plates have only hardening behavior, but positive and negative initial excitation amplitude are not same frequency ratios. For antisymmetric hybrid plate, $[Al/0^\circ_c/90^\circ/Al]$, increase of aspect ratio results in increase of nonlinearity. Nonlinearity of $[0^\circ/Al]_s$ layer-up is higher than that of $[90^\circ/Al]_s$, and for $[\theta^\circ/Al]_s$, the increase of Young's modulus decreases nonlinearity. In case of $[Al/\theta^\circ]_s$, it is reverse. And the linear fundamental frequency of $[0^\circ/Al]_s$ layer-up has larger than that of $[90^\circ/Al]_s$.

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Table 1. Material properties of used materials

Material	Aluminium	GFRP	CFRP	BFRP
E_1	72.0GPa	38.6GPa	181. GPa	204. GPa
E_2	72.0GPa	8.27GPa	10.3GPa	18.5GPa
G_{12}	28.0GPa	4.14GPa	7.17GPa	5.59GPa
ρ	2700kg/m ³	1800kg/m ³	1600kg/m ³	2000kg/m ³
ν_{12}	0.33	0.26	0.28	0.23
Abbrev.	Al	B	C	B

Table 2. Comparison of frequency ratios with Ref.[8] for $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ CFRP square, rectangular plates ($E_1/E_2=40, E_2/G_{12}=5, \nu_{12}=0.25$)

$\frac{W_n}{h}$	Frequency Ratios (ω_n/ω_1)					
	Square plate (a/b=1)		Rec. plate (a/b=2)			
	Present Ref. [8]	Diff.	Present Ref. [8]	Diff.		
.3	1.0825	1.0796	0.268	0.9437	0.9448	0.117
.6	1.2651	1.2867	1.707	0.9584	0.9568	0.167
.9	1.5672	1.5691	0.121	1.1424	1.1432	0.070
1.2	1.9091	1.8933	0.828	1.4358	1.4376	0.125
1.5	2.2340	2.2414	0.331	1.7826	1.7826	0.000
1.8	2.5610	2.6040	1.679	2.1579	2.1521	0.269
2.1	3.0000	2.9759	0.803	2.5448	2.5341	0.420
2.4	3.2813	3.3541	2.219	2.9055	2.9235	0.620
2.7	3.6207	3.7366	3.201	3.3243	3.3172	0.214

Diff. : Difference

(a) Plate geometry and coordinate system

(b) Section geometry

Figure 1. Geometry and coordinate system of a plate and its section

Table 3. Linear natural frequencies of square hybrid composite plates for various stacking sequences and material properties

	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(1,3)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(2,3)
$[0^\circ/A]_{BFRP}$	ABAQUS	237.62	414.47	769.07	833.10	947.83	1210.6
	ANALYTIC	238.38	415.80	772.20	836.82	956.94	1212.1
$[0^\circ/A]_{CFRP}$	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(1,3)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(1,4)
	ABAQUS	236.42	398.14	714.42	826.86	943.39	1178.3
$[0^\circ/A]_{CFRP}$	ANALYTIC	237.25	400.00	716.85	829.88	947.87	1183.4
	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(1,3)	(2,3)
$[0^\circ/A]_{CFRP}$	ABAQUS	149.88	327.27	444.50	599.05	636.97	885.86
	ANALYTIC	150.72	364.30	445.43	604.23	638.98	888.89
$[0^\circ/A]_{CFRP}$	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(1,3)	(2,3)
	ABAQUS	259.29	628.67	685.37	1034.4	1252.9	1400.3
$[0^\circ/A]_{CFRP}$	ANALYTIC	262.12	634.92	692.04	1047.1	1257.9	1418.4
	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(1,3)	(3,1)
$[A/0^\circ]_{CFRP}$	ABAQUS	269.38	653.74	708.66	1074.9	1301.8	1444.8
	ANALYTIC	272.11	660.07	716.85	1092.9	1307.2	1459.9
$[A/0^\circ]_{CFRP}$	MODE	(1,1)	(1,2)	(2,1)	(2,2)	(1,3)	(3,1)
	ABAQUS	254.82	634.12	644.05	1016.8	1268.0	1298.0
$[A/0^\circ]_{CFRP}$	ANALYTIC	258.06	638.98	651.47	1036.3	1273.9	1307.2

Figure 2. Variation of nondimensional amplitude with time for $[0_0^/90_0^]$ antisymmetric square and rectangular cross-ply plates

Figure 3. Frequency ratio vs nondimensional amplitudes of antisymmetric hybrid plates for various stacking sequences

Figure 4. Frequency ratio vs nondimensional amplitude of $[Al/0c/90c/Al]$ plate for various aspect ratio

Figure 5. Frequency ratio vs nondimensional amplitudes of $[Al/0c]_s$ plate for half wave numbers

Figure 6. Frequency ratio vs nondimensional amplitudes of $[\theta/Al]_s$ plate for various stacking sequences and elastic properties

Figure 7. Frequency ratio vs nondimensional amplitudes of $[Al/\theta]_s$ plate for various stacking sequences and elastic properties